

**THE UNITY OF UMMAH THROUGH PURIFICATION OF SOUL
(TAZKIYYAH AL-NAFS) IN AL-QURAN**

by

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ABSTRACT

The unity of ummah has been mentioned many times in al-Quran. It is pivotal in Islam as a fundamental strength to develop and manage Muslim community in a country to a betterment of life in this world and hereafter. However, the existence of the different opinions and methodologies that lead to the establishment of various school of thoughts are inescapable due to ordinary internal and external factors that emerged. Such different phenomenon creates worse and chaos if the ethics of disagreement have been disappeared from the true purification of soul. In fact, al-Quran mentions many times the importance of purification of soul as the central of goodness, virtues and solidarity. This practice was exercised seriously by the Prophet and his companions as well as their followers until they were well recognized as the most excellent ummah in their era. This discourse uses historical and content analysis study to explain the relationship between the purification of soul with the unity of ummah. Finally, the unity of ummah is possible to be achieved through purification of soul as urged in al-Quran by sharing a similar ultimate purpose of life, responsibility and behaving with the praiseworthy qualities based on tawhid orientation.

Keywords: unity, ummah, purification of soul, al-Quran

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Introduction

In the Muslim world, the issue of the unity of *ummah* is always be discussed with the endless solution and effort. The unity of Muslim *ummah* is mentioned nine times in the Holy Qur'an as *ummah wahidah*. Allah says:

إِنَّ هَذِهِ أُمَّتُكُمْ أُمَّةً وَاحِدَةً وَأَنَا رَبُّكُمْ فَاعْبُدُونِ (92)

Indeed, this brotherhood of yours is one brotherhood based on the one basic foundation, and I am your Lord, therefore worship Me (Alone) (al-anbiya' 21: 92)

The question raised is how to understand the concept of the unity of *ummah* and to manifest it in life in al-Quran. In fact, in the reality, Muslim community live in many differences in thought, culture, race, and language

Throughout scrutinizing Muslims scholarly literatures about the issue of disunity, and differences until the emergence of the various schools of thought in Islamic history, such as Abdul Qahir al-Baghdadi, Muhammad Abu Zahrah, Muhammad Zaki Ibrahim, and others, the factors cause to that can be simplified into two main factors; external and internal

The major external factors can be summarized as follow: the first, misperception meaning of differences of opinions as contradiction and conflicting each other. The second is following the schools of thought (*mazahib*) with fanatical emotion. The third, confusing between fundamental and branches matter in Islam and priority. Perceiving the branches as fundamental and the fundamental is branches. This factor may be lead to charge another Muslim as heretical easily and unconsciously. The forth, the misunderstanding of leadership's issue become aqidah issue.

In fact, such factors and strengthened by the internal factors which can be considered as soul Illness that is an allusion of Shaitan and following command of the evil soul (*nafs al-ammarah*),

For the first, Shaitan always plays his role to deceit Muslim to the enmity, confusing and forgetting Allah command. Moreover, shaitan can control Muslim in the state of extremely angry, disappointed, sexual desire and sadness. Shaitan creates the allusion that the wrong is true and the true is wrong

وَزَيَّنَ لَهُمُ الشَّيْطَانُ أَعْمَالَهُمْ فَصَدَّهُمْ عَنِ السَّبِيلِ وَكَانُوا مُسْتَبْصِرِينَ

Shaitan who made their (foul) deeds seem fair to them, and kept them back from the right path of Allah, though they were gifted with intelligence and skill (and were able to distinguish between right and wrong). (al-Ankabut 29:38)

The second, evil soul (*nafs al-Ammarah bi al-Su'*), its nature is to disobey, rebel and transgress the command of Allah. It also behaves with animalistic behavior and destructive blameworthy qualities such as treason, envy, lying, arrogant and others. Allah says clearly.

وَمَا أَبْرَأُ نَفْسِي إِنَّ النَّفْسَ لَأَمَّارَةٌ بِالسُّوءِ إِلَّا مَا رَحِمَ رَبِّي إِنَّ رَبِّي غَفُورٌ رَحِيمٌ

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And yet, I am not trying to absolve myself: the human soul often incites to evil except him to whom my Lord bestows His Mercy . Verily, my Lord is Most Forgiving, Most Merciful (yusuf 12:53)

When shaitan and evil soul overpower on the belief and rationality, so that Muslim involves in mistake and committing many wrongdoings such as crime and harmful to the others

To overcome this factor, Muslim needs a way to purify the soul and rectify perception. The way to purify the soul is by having a true education (*tarbiyyah*), striving (*mujahadah*) and consistent exercise (*riyadah*) In Islam, purification of soul is compulsory as stated in al-Quran and agreed by many reputable scholars such as Abu Hamid Muhammad bin Muhammad al-Ghazzali, Abdul Wahhab al-Sha'rani Ahmad bin Abdul Ahad al-Sirhindi, and others. This is because one cannot escape from behaving blameworthy qualities except the Prophets. Allah says,

هُوَ الَّذِي بَعَثَ فِي الْأُمِّيِّينَ رَسُولًا مِنْهُمْ يَتْلُو عَلَيْهِمْ آيَاتِهِ وَيُزَكِّيهِمْ وَيُعَلِّمُهُمُ الْكِتَابَ وَالْحِكْمَةَ وَإِنْ كَانُوا مِنْ قَبْلُ لَفِي ضَلَالٍ مُبِينٍ

He it is Who has sent among the unlettered (Arabs) a Messenger (Muhammad) from among themselves, reciting to them His Verses, purifying them (from deviation in their belief) and teaching them the Book (this Qur'an), and Wisdom . And verily, they had been before in manifest error (al-jumaah 62:2)

In education, Muslim needs true knowledge and sincere practice under the supervision of a good teacher in cleansing the soul. A good teacher has the ability to provide a way to purification of soul can be known as *ahl al-dhikr* as he has the expertise to train it. Allah says:

فَاسْأَلُوا أَهْلَ الذِّكْرِ إِنْ كُنْتُمْ لَا تَعْلَمُونَ

so ask the people of the Reminder if you do not know (al-anbiya' 21: 7)

Even reputable scholars in esoteric knowledge, they still need a master due to man is fallible and vulnerable to behave with blameworthy qualities that destroy all deeds. In fact, many great prominent scholars admit this fact such as Muhammad bin Muhammad al-Ghazzali (d.505H/1111M) got lesson and practice from Abu Ali al-Farmadi (d. 477H/1084M) Abd al-Wahhab al-Sha'rani (d.973H/1565M) got from Ali al-Khawwas (d.969H/1532M), Abd al-Ahad al-Sirhindi (d. 1034H/1624M) got from Muhammad al-Baqi (d.1012H/1603M), Abdul Samad al-Falimbangi (d. 1247H/1832M) got from Muhammad bin Abd al-Karim al-Madani (d.1189H/ 1776M) and others.

Hence, Ibrahim bin Abd al-Aziz al-Dasuqi (d1296H/1879M) says that if the shari'ah obligation is not displayed with the immaterial casualties and soul illness, so that one is self-sufficient from shaykh. Due to the obstacles exists in the form of casualties and illness, so one requires necessarily the shaykh to guide him performing the shari'ah's duties like one demand a medical doctor to treat his disease until he feels cured (al-Sha'rani n.d.,)

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Mujahadah is the utilization of maximum effort physically, intellectually and spiritually to perform the shariah's teaching by against the demand of evil soul. To soften the soul and alter its nature from evil to tranquility soul (*nafs mutamainnah*) Muslim must strive to practice the shariah teaching intertwined with much of remembrance of Allah verbally and silence in the heart. In fact, by remembering Allah, it erases blameworthy qualities, strengthens the belief in the heart from conceptual to tasted belief and certainty (*haq al-yaqin*). In addition, it eradicates all shaitan allusion, doubtful and ambiguity in belief. Meanwhile, it helps to make the performance of shari'ah become easy and results in a strong willing to exercise it voluntarily with a calm heart (al-Sirhindi n.d)

وَالَّذِينَ جَاهَدُوا فِينَا لَنَهْدِيَنَّهُمْ سُبُلَنَا وَإِنَّ اللَّهَ لَمَعَ الْمُحْسِنِينَ

As for those who strive hard for Our cause, We will surely guide them to Our Paths. And verily, Allah is with the those who do good .(al-Ankabut 29:69)

The exercise, it means to practice all the shari'ah teaching constantly until it becomes a permanent habit in Muslim personality. So it enlightens Muslim with consistency in belief and virtue deed with praiseworthy qualities such as patience, gratitude, sincerity and other. Allah says:

إِنَّ الَّذِينَ قَالُوا رَبُّنَا اللَّهُ ثُمَّ اسْتَقَامُوا فَلَا خَوْفٌ عَلَيْهِمْ وَلَا هُمْ يَحْزَنُونَ

those who affirm their belief by saying say: "Our Lord is (only) Allah," and thereafter folow firmly the straight path shall have nothing to fear, nor shall they grieve.(al-ahqaf 46:13)

By a combination of *tarbiyyah*, *mujahadah* and *tarbiyyah*, the soul can be cleansed from any created veil and illness. The clean soul located in the heart as an immaterial spiritual substance that controls the mind and physical sense to perform all duties sincerely with the Constance presence of heart to Allah. All scholars agree that fighting the evil desire is the main cause to achieve the pleasure in this world and hereafter (al-Ghazzali 1996). It is in line with Allah's saying,

وَأَمَّا مَنْ خَافَ مَقَامَ رَبِّهِ وَنَهَى النَّفْسَ عَنِ الْهَوَىٰ فَإِنَّ الْجَنَّةَ هِيَ الْمَأْوَىٰ

But as for him who feared standing before his Lord, and restrained himself from impure evil desires, and lusts. Verily, Paradise will be his abode (al-Nazi'at 79:40-41)

The concept of the differences of ummah should be reviewed in a wide context. In Islamic history, different viewpoints were happened since in period of prophet Muhammad SAW, his companions and the Followers (*Tabi'in*). It is human nature to have different opinions and way in understanding within the circle and light al-Quran. Muslim must understand the differences are not inevitably drive to disunity. The differences of opinion do not allude the as contradiction and conflicting, in fact, it rather means as an expansion and diversity of wide teaching of Islam within the composition of accommodation and strictest mode by taking into a consideration the level of strength of Muslim physically and spiritually as a wide blessing from Allah (al-Sha'rani, n.d).

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The true perception of schools of thoughts (*mazahib*) also should be rectified in a new outlook. The emergence of many schools of thoughts in theology such as al-ashairah, al-Maturidiyyah, and others, jurisprudents such as Hanafiyyah, Malikiyyah, Shafiyyah, Hanabillah, and Sufism such as Naqhabandiyyah, Shazilliyyah, Shattariyyah, and others are not identical as a religion, but they are rather as a metaphorical inscription and methodology in clarifying the detailed meaning of Islam. The different viewpoint occurs among them relates to a matter of branches of religion due to dissimilar ways of outlook, clarification, deduction and seeking the truth.

In fact, to know the real knowledge and teaching of al-Quran cannot be obtained directly unless by referring to their elaboration that got the knowledge from their previous serial connection of teachers until to the prophet Muhammad. Hence following the *mazahib* should not be fanatic but more to look like a mechanism to ease Muslim to understand and practice the teaching of Islam correctly.

Regarding the matter of fundamental and branches in religion. Muslim must conscious both nature until no harmful and accusation of heretical among Muslim. The matter of branches should not be polemical as it depends on the reliability of the source and level of understanding it. It rather a matter to find a way to implement and achieve the goal in religion.

Generally all the followers of various schools of thought are sharing similar fundamental that is *la ila ill allah and muhammad rasul Allah* so that .they are regarded as *muslimin* and *ahl al-qiblah* even they are inaccuracy in interpretation of some branches matter in religion , In fact, all of them are Unitarian Muslim (*muwahidun*) and entering the paradise.

Relating the misunderstanding of leadership's issue as identical to aqidah issue. It must be conceived correctly that the issue of leadership is juristic subject nor aqidah . The polemic of leadership actually based on the *ijthad* in way of managing and ruling to attain the purpose in religion. In fact, it is medium to help Muslim to perform the duties in this world. Good performance duties in religion rely in the well-organized management of worldly affair, the good management of worldly affair is relaying to excellent management and leadership of the leader. Indeed, the world is a bridge to the hereafter (al-Ghazzali 1996).

Although the phenomenon of differences are inevitable and as human nature, so the concept of the unity of ummah is still possible to be attained. It can be realized by sharing similar clear objective in life according to the Quranic perspective.

The first, acknowledging the ultimate objective of man created in this world as khalifah of Allah, His servant and excellent human to shoulder the religious duties that manifest Muslim acknowledgment of the Lordship and divinity of Allah .

وَمَا خَلَقْتُ الْجِنَّ وَالْإِنْسَ إِلَّا لِيَعْبُدُونِ

And I (Allah) created not the jinns and humans except they should worship Me (Alone) Al-Dhariyat 51:56

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إِنِّي جَاعِلٌ فِي الْأَرْضِ خَلِيفَةً

I am going to place vicegerent on the earth (al-Baqarah 2:30)

Historically, all men are purity and unity before living in this material world. Men during their existence in pure spiritual being had witnessed a covenant firmly in constant remembrance the lordship and divinity of Allah in the world of spirit. However, after their existence in the material form in this world, most of them are forgetful that covenant. Allah says:

أَلَسْتُ بِرَبِّكُمْ قَالُوا بَلَى شَهِدْنَا أَنْ تَقُولُوا يَوْمَ الْقِيَامَةِ إِنَّا كُنَّا عَنْ هَذَا غَافِلِينَ

Am I not your Lord?" They said: "Yes! Indeed, We testify," so that on the Day of Resurrection: "Truly we have been unaware of this (al-A'raf 7:172)

Therefore Allah send serial of prophets and messengers until to the last message of Muhammad SAW to educate, remind and guide men to remember that covenant. In the period of Prophetic Muhammad SAW all men are taught to remember the covenant with firm conviction in the heart of all fundamental belief by confessing verbally similar word of *shahadah* in the present tense that *ashadu alla ilaha illa Allah wa ashadu anna muhammad rasulullah*. The word of *shahadah* consisted of three important meaning, absolute conviction, belief and affirmation the truth.

Sharing similar all basic religion responsibility collectively to practice Islam in order to obtain happiness in this world and hereafter. It also means to perform all commandments of Allah and stay away from His prohibitions such as killing without rights, stealing, backbiting, adultery, and others. For instance, performing prayer five-time collectively regardless of different *mazahib* with sharing similar niche Qiblah of Kaabah in Makkah. Lastly, all Muslim deeds are accountable from a sincere deed.

وَارْكَعُوا مَعَ الرَّاكِعِينَ

bow down (in congregation) with those who bow down (al-baqarah 2:43)

لَنْ يَنَالَ اللَّهُ لُحُومُهَا وَلَا دِمَاؤُهَا وَلَكِنْ يَنَالُهُ التَّقْوَىٰ مِنْكُمْ

The flesh and blood of the sacrificial animal do not reach Allah but it is piety from you that reaches Him (al-hajj 22:37)

Behaving with praiseworthy qualities as a universal value crossing the culture, race, language, and geography. All Muslim admit the praiseworthy qualities such as love, patience, gratitude, sincerity, humbleness, and mutual help, brotherhood and others. All these good behaviors and traits are clearly and obviously mentioned in al-Quran.

It means all Muslim in the world must behave a similar good and praiseworthy attitude that unite all Muslim regardless who they are, and the differences in thought, *mazahib* and others. These praiseworthy qualities are manifest clearly the unity of ummah particularly during

performing pilgrimage (hajj) in Makkah. Without such good qualities in pilgrimage duties, all Muslim are unable to do it properly in a massive manner.

الْحَجُّ أَشْهُرٌ مَعْلُومَاتٌ فَمَنْ فَرَضَ فِيهِنَّ الْحَجَّ فَلَا رَفَثَ وَلَا فُسُوقَ وَلَا جِدَالَ فِي الْحَجِّ
وَمَا تَفَعَّلُوا مِنْ خَيْرٍ يَعْلَمُهُ اللَّهُ وَتَرَوُودُوا فَإِنَّ خَيْرَ الزَّادِ التَّقْوَى وَاتَّقُونِ يَا أُولِي الْأَلْبَابِ

The *Hajj* (pilgrimage) is (in) the well-known (lunar year) months. So whosoever intends to perform *Hajj* therein then he should not have sexual relations (with his wife), nor commit sin, nor dispute unjustly during the *Hajj*. And whatever good you do, (be sure) Allah knows it. And take a provision (with you) for the journey, but the best provision is *At-Taqwa* (piety, righteousness, etc.). So fear Me, O you endowed with insight (al-Baqarah 2:197)

From this discourse, it can be said, the difference can be divided into type; blameworthy difference and praiseworthy difference. The first is the different causes to disunity that comprised of fanatical, extreme, evil assumption and harmful the others physically, emotionally, and spiritually the others. However, the praiseworthy difference does not lead to disunity but to lead to the unity of Muslim ummah by sharing a similar fundamental purpose in Islam. All the differences have its meeting point for similarity and unity that is a purification of soul and rectification of misperception with true fact. However the unity of Muslim ummah also does not mean Muslim will not make any mistake or sin consciously or unconsciously, but the way to improve it is, always seeking forgiveness and constant repentance to Allah as He is the Forgiver and Merciful.

It can be said that the differences occur in a form, not to the real essence teaching of Islam. The differences are posited as a various way to achieve one purpose that Is Allah's pleasure. Allah says:

قُلْ كُلٌّ يَعْمَلُ عَلَى شَاكِلَتِهِ فَرَبُّكُمْ أَعْلَمُ بِمَنْ هُوَ أَهْدَى سَبِيلًا

Say (O Muhammad) "Each one acts according to his own disposition and your Lord best knows among you is best guided on the way (al-isra' 17:84)

Finally, it can be concluded that the unity of Muslim ummah from Quranic perspective is possible and reality to be achieved. . It can be regarded as unity in multiplicity from the aspect of sharing similar objective, performing responsibility collectively and behaving with similar praiseworthy qualities based on a clean soul and tawhidic orientation.

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